

WOMEN AND ECONOMIC AUTONOMY: ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE BEAUTY INDUSTRY AS A SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY

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Alana Aparecida Vierzynski Ciechinski

*Student of Accounting Sciences, State University of the Midwest – UNICENTRO. Mallet,
Paraná, Brazil. E-mail: alanavierzynski.22@gmail.com*

Telma Regina Stroparo

Doctor, Professor, State University of the Midwest – UNICENTRO . Irati, Paraná, Brazil.

Email: telma@unicentro.br

ABSTRACT

Female entrepreneurship has consolidated itself as a relevant strategy for income generation and the expansion of women's economic autonomy, particularly in historically feminized and labor-intensive sectors such as the beauty industry. Although women-led enterprises have grown significantly in recent decades, financial sustainability remains one of the main challenges faced by female entrepreneurs. This fragility is largely associated with informality, lack of structured financial planning, and limited use of accounting tools for managerial purposes. In this context, this theoretical article aims to analyze how managerial accounting can contribute to financial sustainability and to the strengthening of women's economic autonomy in the beauty sector. Based on a literature review addressing female entrepreneurship, economic inequalities, and accounting practices applied to small businesses, the study argues that instruments such as cash flow control, cost analysis, strategic pricing, financial planning, and profitability assessment function as structuring mechanisms for economic stability and risk reduction. Accounting, when understood as a managerial tool rather than merely a fiscal requirement, assumes a strategic role in economic organization, supporting profitability preservation and sustainable growth. The article contributes by articulating gender, financial management, and accounting as key elements in the consolidation of women-led enterprises and in the promotion of women's economic autonomy.

Keywords: Female entrepreneurship. Economic autonomy. Managerial accounting. Financial sustainability. Gender perspective.

INTRODUCTION

Women's entrepreneurship has become a central axis in contemporary discussions on sustainable development and economic inclusion, reflecting the growing recognition of the

intersection between gender, business, and sustainability (Limón et al., 2025). International literature highlights that women's participation in entrepreneurial activity not only contributes to economic growth and poverty reduction but also promotes more socially oriented management models, in which innovation, social responsibility, and collective well-being coexist with financial objectives (Raman et al., 2022; Sarpong ; Nyuur ; Torbor , 2021; Stroparo ; Cordiak , 2021)

However, despite their strategic role in global development, women continue to face structural inequalities in access to credit, capital, and market opportunities, resulting in systematically lower rates of entrepreneurial activity than those observed among men and disproportionate levels of profitability (Batista; Sequeira; Vicente, 2021; Lladós-Masllorens ; Dotras , 2021). In the Brazilian context, these barriers are particularly evident, since a large proportion of women become entrepreneurs out of necessity, concentrating in sectors with low barriers to entry such as fashion, food, and beauty, segments that, although relevant for generating immediate income, present high financial vulnerability and greater exposure to the risk of insolvency (Santos et al., 2022).

Among these sectors, the beauty segment stands out for its social reach and strong female presence, but also for high rates of informality and weaknesses in financial management. The absence of systematic management control instruments, coupled with low financial literacy, compromises the capacity for planning, saving, investing, and sustainable business expansion (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024; Sherwani ; Shaikh ; Siddiqui , 2023). Studies demonstrate that deficits in financial and numerical skills directly impact business performance, limiting strategic pricing, cost control, and cash flow management—decisive factors for the survival of micro and small businesses (Batista; Sequeira; Vicente, 2021; Muñoz-Céspedes; Ibar-Alonso; Mir, 2023; Stroparo et al., 2024).

Literature on financial literacy indicates that the ability to interpret economic information, assess risks, and plan future decisions is a critical determinant of business performance and organizational resilience (Venesaar et al., 2021; Alshebami ; Murad, 2022). When acquired by women entrepreneurs, these skills enhance self-efficacy, strengthen risk tolerance, and boost entrepreneurial intention (Lladós-Masllorens ; Dotras , 2021).

In this sense, managerial accounting ceases to represent a mere fiscal obligation and becomes a strategic instrument for economic organization, risk mitigation, and financial consolidation (Staziacki ; Stroparo , 2023).

From a capabilities perspective, economic autonomy is not limited to income generation, but involves expanding the concrete conditions for exercising free and informed

choices (Kumar et al., 2022; Xu ; Jiang, 2024). Effective financial management, based on disciplined control practices, cost analysis, and strategic planning, acts as a mechanism for strengthening women's agency, allowing the enterprise to transcend subsistence and reach sustainable levels of competitiveness and stability (Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025).

In this scenario, a gap persists in the articulation between gender, financial literacy, and formal management accounting instruments as structuring mechanisms for women's economic autonomy, especially in sectors intensive in informality, such as the beauty industry.

Given this scenario, this article aims to analyze, from a gender perspective, how management accounting can contribute to financial sustainability and the strengthening of women's economic autonomy in the beauty sector. By articulating gender, financial literacy, and accounting management, the study seeks to fill a gap in the literature that still treats these fields in a fragmented way, proposing accounting as a strategic technology for economic empowerment and the reduction of structural vulnerabilities.

METHODOLOGY

This study is characterized as theoretical research with a qualitative approach, grounded in an interpretative epistemological perspective . As highlighted by Guerra et al. (2024), qualitative research relies on a deep understanding of social phenomena through the interpretation of meanings, contexts, and structures that shape human practices. In this sense, female entrepreneurship, economic autonomy, and managerial accounting are understood as socially situated phenomena, whose analysis requires an interpretative and contextualized approach.

The methodological strategy consisted of a structured literature review, guided by criteria of thematic relevance, theoretical consistency, and timeliness. Keywords in Portuguese and English were used, including *female. entrepreneurship* , *economic autonomy* , *financial literacy* , *managerial accounting* and *small business financial management* .

The analysis of the studies followed a hermeneutic approach, understood as an interpretative process that seeks to identify convergences, gaps, and tensions between different theoretical contributions. Thus, the article is organized into three analytical axes: (i) structural gender inequalities in entrepreneurship; (ii) literacy and financial competence as determinants of business performance; and (iii) management accounting as a strategic instrument for financial sustainability and strengthening women's economic autonomy.

Thus, the methodology adopted aligns with the fundamentals of qualitative research by prioritizing theoretical interpretation and the construction of conceptual articulations capable of supporting the analytical proposition of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Women's entrepreneurship: international concepts and perspectives

International literature has recognized female entrepreneurship as a distinct analytical category, capable of challenging androcentric assumptions in economic theory and traditional models of organizational performance. Instead of conceiving entrepreneurial activity as a separate and exclusively rational sphere, recent studies indicate that female entrepreneurs frequently operate under logics of *embeddedness*, in which the venture is intertwined with family, community, and cultural relationships that influence motivations, decisions, and growth strategies (Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025).

In this debate, authors associated with the contextual perspective of entrepreneurship argue that the supposed gender neutrality obscures power mechanisms that maintain structural asymmetries, normalizing the figure of the entrepreneur as universal and socially unmarked. This universalization produces analytical gaps by neglecting institutional, sociocultural, and symbolic barriers that shape female entrepreneurship in different realities (Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025).

In societies permeated by patriarchal structures, such as Brazil, the social assignment of care to women intensifies tensions between traditional expectations and business aspirations, requiring constant negotiations between personal and professional life (Ayatakshi-Endow ; Steele, 2021).

Furthermore, critical literature points out that approaches based on masculine growth patterns may label women's businesses as "underproductive" by ignoring that women's entrepreneurial motivations often include relational, community, and well-being goals, which cannot be reduced to profit maximization (Kawarazuka et al., 2023; Kini, 2022).

Added to this is the risk of homogenizing "women entrepreneurs" as a monolithic group. The incorporation of intersectional perspectives shows that gender is articulated with race, class, and territory, producing differentiated inequalities in access to markets, credit, and support networks, which requires analyses sensitive to the heterogeneity of trajectories (Oliveira; Basini ; Cooney , 2024; Onoshakpor ; Cunningham; Gammie , 2024; Maharjan ; Nazir ; Roomi , 2024; Shah; Hayes; Obaid , 2024).

Economic autonomy and empowerment: contributions from gender and development studies.

Economic autonomy, in this discussion, is not limited to income generation, but relates to the ability to make strategic choices and control resources with effects on well-being, entrepreneurship, and family life. This conception is close to the concept of *agency*, understood as the ability to act, define goals, and produce changes, the effectiveness of which depends on contextual conditions and the social position occupied by women (Kini , 2022; Canelas; Selhausen ; Stam , 2024).

In this sense, economic empowerment is interpreted as a process of transforming asymmetrical power relations, in which autonomy emerges from the interaction between resources, agency, and results achieved (Ng ; Wood; Bastian , 2022; Calderón; Maestriperi , 2022).

Kabeer 's empowerment model reinforces that material and immaterial resources (financial, human, and social capital) constitute preconditions for the exercise of agency, but do not, by themselves, guarantee decision-making power. The conversion of resources into autonomy and well-being is mediated by social norms, institutional structures, and effectively available opportunities (Manasoe ; Mmbengwa ; Lekunze , 2022; Ranabahu ; Tanima , 2021; Sarker et al., 2024).

Thus, the discussion shifts from the simple possession of assets to the ability to use them under concrete conditions of choice, highlighting that economic autonomy is always relational and structured by normative environments that can expand or restrict opportunities (Riddle et al., 2023; Nath; Das, 2024; Lwamba et al., 2022; Saaka ; Luginaah , 2025).

Management accounting, by producing information for planning, control and decision-making, assumes a central role in the viability of micro and small businesses, especially in contexts of low capitalization and high volatility (Staziacki ; Stroparo , 2023).

For women-led businesses, the adoption of tools such as cash flow, cost analysis, and pricing constitutes a mechanism for reducing financial vulnerabilities and transitioning from informality to management oriented towards economic continuity (Atarah et al., 2023; Ranabahu ; Tanima , 2021).

The absence of systematic records and controls widens informational asymmetries, weakens revenue predictability, and hinders expense control, increasing the risks of default and business discontinuation. Recent literature has associated managerial control practices with

organizational resilience, understood as the capacity to resist, adapt to, and recover from external shocks.

In this context, timely financial information systems, budgeting, indicator monitoring, and continuity plans favor risk anticipation and strategic response to adverse scenarios (Hashem ; Hashem , 2023; Roffia ; Dabić , 2023; Koporčić et al., 2025).

The incorporation of digital technologies can reinforce this process by reducing informational asymmetries and expanding the capacity for data-driven management (Akintobi ; Okeke ; Ajani , 2024).

The intersection between gender studies and management accounting shows that financial sustainability in women-led businesses depends less on the abstract "availability" of resources and more on the ability to structure management practices that convert resources into decision-making autonomy.

In this scenario, resilience is not simply an individual attribute: it is a strategic capacity, built through informational governance, planning, and risk mitigation mechanisms (Roffia & Dabić , 2023; Weber & Pedell & Rötzel , 2024; Eichholz & Hoffmann & Schwering , 2024). Gender-oriented literature also suggests that coping and sustainability strategies can take on relational and community-based forms, often overlooked in management models focused on self-sufficiency and competition, reinforcing the need for accounting structures capable of translating these dynamics into economic intelligence to support decisions (Shamieh & Bastian , 2025).

Entrepreneurship in the beauty industry as a strategy for women's sustainability.

The beauty sector, characterized by low barriers to entry and a strong relational component, constitutes a privileged field for observing how management accounting can transform informality into economically viable management. The social reach of the activity and the mobilization of relational capital can favor access to clientele and markets; however, the business's longevity requires professionalization of financial management, especially regarding the separation between personal and business finances, systematic recording of transactions, and liquidity control. Beyond economic results, sustainability in the sector involves dimensions frequently prioritized by female entrepreneurs, such as work-life balance and impacts on family and community well-being (Palakshappa ; Dodds ; Grant, 2023).

These dimensions reinforce that the economic rationality of the undertaking should not be dissociated from the gender contexts that shape time, choices, and responsibilities (León-Gómez et al., 2023; Pierli ; Murmura; Palazzi , 2022).

The systematic use of financial instruments such as cash flow control, cost analysis, and strategic pricing acts as a mechanism to mitigate economic hardship by allowing for the anticipation of liquidity bottlenecks, preservation of margins, and reduction of dependence on high-cost credit.

Evidence-based management, in contrast to intuitive decisions, favors maintaining solvency and reducing default rates (Miranda et al., 2022). The literature also indicates that financial competence and digital literacy are associated with better economic performance in women-led companies, enhancing the ability to analyze scenarios and make strategic decisions (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024; Peter; Geetha ; Gupta, 2024).

Cash flow functions as a liquidity management tool, while the segregation between fixed and variable costs allows for understanding the economic structure of the business and identifying waste. Budgets and financial forecasts, in turn, enhance planning capacity, anticipate capital needs, and guide investment and expansion decisions (Odonkor et al., 2024). By strengthening the consistency of financial information, such practices can also improve relationships with financial institutions, creating conditions for access to credit on a more stable basis (Kurniasari ; Hamid; Lestari , 2025).

When appropriated as a management tool, accounting can operate as a social technology for economic organization, making visible the financial dynamics of often invisible enterprises and supporting evidence-based decisions. Financial literacy, which involves recording income and expenses, asset separation, and planning, constitutes a resource for stability and sustainable growth, reducing informational asymmetries and expanding the capacity for economic agency (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024; Lestari et al., 2025).

The internalization of systematic accounting practices strengthens credibility and bargaining power, and can act as a mechanism for social transformation by reconfiguring economic power relations and expanding conditions for autonomy in historically restrictive environments (Batista; Sequeira; Vicente, 2021; Medina-Vidal et al., 2025; Bohorquez ; Sánchez, 2023).

In this sense, entrepreneurial resilience should be understood as a contextual and gendered process , dependent on access to capital, networks and information, as well as adaptive capacities supported by financial management tools (Bagheri et al., 2023; Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025).

Accounting as a Social Technology and Instrument for Women's Economic Empowerment

Accounting, by transcending its traditional function of measurement and recording, is configured as a social technology of economic organization that structures reality and enables rational action in contexts of resource scarcity.

The appropriation of this technical knowledge allows women entrepreneurs not only to navigate uncertain market environments, but also to challenge power structures that have historically limited their access to financial resources and support networks (Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025) .

The internalization of systematic accounting practices, such as detailed transaction recording and analysis of financial statements, transforms information management into a strategic asset that enhances women's negotiating power and innovation capacity (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024; Kurniasari et al., 2026) .

Studies indicate that the development of financial management skills persists over time and positively impacts business performance, suggesting that internalizing these practices promotes a lasting change in how women conduct their businesses (Batista; Sequeira; Vicente, 2021) .

This change in managerial behavior, based on the systematic use of accounting information, allows breaking with the logic of informality and precariousness that often marks women's subsistence entrepreneurship, replacing intuition with decisions based on quantitative evidence (Batista; Sequeira; Vicente, 2021; Ichim; Vid, 2025) .

The transformation of accounting into an instrument of economic agency allows women to redefine their position in the market, using information management to mitigate the constraints imposed by the sexual division of labor and precarious income. (Bohorquez ; Sánchez, 2023) The ability to transform financial knowledge into digital participation and market strategies, shaped by social gender constraints, demonstrates that literacy is not a static attribute, but a dynamic system of capabilities that is refined through iterative learning and adaptive decision-making (Nuraisyiah ; Azis ; Hasan, 2025) .

Empirical evidence suggests that the complementarity between financial literacy and access to savings technologies has a positive and lasting effect on the profits and financial security of female micro-entrepreneurs, reducing the performance gap in relation to men (Batista; Sequeira; Vicente, 2021) .

The internalization of accounting practices, therefore, is not limited to operational efficiency, but constitutes a mechanism for social transformation that reconfigures economic power relations by providing women with the legitimacy and credibility necessary to operate in market spaces historically dominated by men.

Financial inclusion, enhanced by literacy skills, creates a virtuous cycle of positive feedback, in which greater access to financial services boosts management capacity and, reciprocally, greater technical qualification expands opportunities for insertion into more competitive markets (Kurniasari et al., 2026) . to navigate volatile business environments and to align operational decisions with long-term sustainability objectives (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024) . for solving complex management problems and for identifying growth opportunities in saturated markets.

The development of complex thinking, which involves integrating multiple perspectives and sources of information to solve problems, therefore becomes a core competency for effective management in highly volatile scenarios (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024) . This cognitive competence integrates systemic, critical, and innovative dimensions, allowing entrepreneurs to synthesize dispersed accounting information into cohesive market strategies (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024)

The intersection between the technical domain of accounting and the cognitive capacity to process complex information is therefore revealed as a critical determinant for overcoming the structural barriers that limit the scope and longevity of women's enterprises, for strategic decision-making and the consolidation of economic autonomy in contexts of uncertainty (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024) , for risk management and maximizing business value in competitive environments.

The ability to transform accounting data into strategic intelligence allows female entrepreneurs to anticipate crisis scenarios and adjust their management models with agility, ensuring the continuity of activities even during periods of economic contraction (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024; Lestari et al., 2025) .

In this sense, proficiency in accounting and financial concepts acts as a catalyst for the development of superior cognitive skills, enabling managers to structure complex problems, identify market patterns, and formulate long-term strategies that go beyond mere daily survival (Bayly-Castaneda et al., 2024) .

The internalization of robust accounting practices, therefore, is not limited to operational efficiency, but constitutes a mechanism of social transformation that reconfigures economic

power relations by providing women with the legitimacy and credibility necessary to operate in market spaces historically dominated by men (Medina-Vidal et al., 2025) .

Adaptive resilience, characterized by the ability to anticipate changes in the competitive environment and strategically reconfigure resources, fundamentally depends on the entrepreneur's confidence in their analytical skills and the systematic use of financial planning tools to mitigate uncertainties (Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025) .

The integration of support networks and the ability to combine diverse information strengthen business resilience, enabling women entrepreneurs to innovate collaboratively and overcome the isolation often imposed by traditional gender structures (Lladós-Masllorens ; Dotras , 2021; Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025). .

In this context, contemporary literature highlights that women entrepreneurs frequently adopt coping strategies focused on emotions, prioritizing relational resources, emotional regulation, and community support, which aligns with gender expectations regarding interconnectedness and relationality. (Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025) .

However, the appreciation of these relational skills should not obscure the critical need for management structures that formalize and measure the economic impact of these interactions, since purely cognitive-behavioral approaches tend to neglect the structural inequalities in access to resources that shape female resilience (Shamieh ; Bastian , 2025) .

Overcoming these inequalities therefore requires recognizing that resilience is a contextual phenomenon in which unequal access to capital, networks, and information determines the capacity of enterprises to respond to and recover from systemic crises (Bagheri et al., 2023; Shamieh & Bastian, 2025) . The literature suggests, however, that process-based resilience models require greater integration of intersectional analyses to capture how gender dynamically interacts with identity markers, such as class and ethnicity, in shaping unique entrepreneurial trajectories Shamieh & Bastian , 2025) .

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This article aimed to analyze how management accounting can contribute to the financial sustainability and strengthening of the economic autonomy of women entrepreneurs in the beauty sector, in light of the contributions of gender studies and the capabilities approach. Based on a structured theoretical review, it was argued that the sustainability of these ventures does not depend exclusively on income generation, but on the ability to structure management

practices that convert economic resources into decisional autonomy and long-term financial stability.

The results of the analysis indicate that managerial accounting, when used as a strategic instrument and not merely as a fiscal obligation, acts as a social technology for economic organization. Tools such as cash flow, cost analysis, contribution margin-oriented pricing, and financial planning constitute concrete mechanisms for mitigating structural vulnerabilities, especially in contexts marked by informality, credit restrictions, and demand volatility. In this sense, the professionalization of financial management favors revenue predictability, expense control, and the creation of reserves, essential elements for organizational resilience.

From a gender perspective, it became evident that economic autonomy should be understood as the expansion of capabilities and the strengthening of agency, not limited to the mere possession of assets or the obtaining of profit. The internalization of systematic accounting practices expands the capacity for strategic decision-making, reinforces negotiating power, and contributes to the reconfiguration of historically imposed economic dependency relationships for women. Thus, accounting emerges as a mediator between resources and achievements, operating as an instrument of economic empowerment.

As a practical implication, it is recommended that public policies and initiatives supporting female entrepreneurship incorporate structured training in management accounting applied to small businesses, with an emphasis on accessible tools and control routines adapted to the reality of micro-entrepreneurs. For future research, it is suggested that empirical investigations be developed to measure the financial impacts of adopting these tools, evaluating indicators of liquidity, profitability, and business survival, in order to empirically test the theoretical propositions discussed here.

In short, financial sustainability in female entrepreneurship, especially in the beauty sector, proves to be inseparable from the strategic appropriation of accounting as an instrument of management, agency, and social transformation.

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